

Investigating the Impact of Enterprise Architecture Adoption in Smart Cities

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Abstract

Enterprise architecture (EA) provides a medium to transform an enterprise and to continually align the institutions business and Information technology (IT) strategies. But, presently Enterprise Architecture (EA) adoption is significantly low irrespective of the benefits organizations can derive from implementing EA. Similarly, there are fewer quantitative studies that examine the impact and benefits of EA towards urban development. Therefore, this research explores the significant issues that influence EA adoption in smart city context. Accordingly, survey data collected from respondents in 18 enterprises based in Norway and Ireland was used to provide evidence on the determinants that influence EA adoption for smart city development and towards the validation of the EA framework that was developed in +CityxChange (<https://cityxchange.eu/>) smart city project. Findings from this study suggest that the developed EA framework supports smart city development. Also, the findings support decision makers in focusing on the main issues that influence EA adoption in urban context. Besides, the findings provide better insights for enterprise architects and practitioners on how their EA deployment plan and strategies can facilitate smart city development.

Keywords: Information systems; Enterprise architecture adoption; IT practitioners; Smart cities; Urban development; Survey questionnaire.

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1. Introduction

Enterprise Architecture (EA) provides several benefits to organizations as it supports interoperability and agility, facilitate decision making in IT deployment, lessens IT costs, etc. [1]. It provides support and direction in the design, transformation, and management of business process to support organizational development. It also entails the representation of a high-level view of an institution's IT systems and business processes, their interrelationships, and the degree to which these IT systems and processes are shared by several parts of the organization [2]. EA can guide the transformation of an enterprise by managing the use and development of information systems. It aids in describing the organizational business strategy, technologies, data, and Information System (IS) on different levels based on the current and future states [3]. EA can primarily be used for guiding the realization of organizational initiatives to support business and IT planning, communication, strategic management, and decision-making [4].

EA also help decision maker for quality assessment [3]. Currently, EA is mostly adopted in industries and governmental institutions to manage IT landscape, as a continuously changing process for enterprises [5]. EA helps to supports stakeholders to plan and develop projects and possibly guides IT managers and Chief Information Officer (CIOs) in skills development and the allocation of IT human resources [6]. Thus, EA can be seen as a process (in terms of definition) and as a product (employed for representation) [3]. EA documentation that are being employed comprises of standards, architectural models, principles, and other resources aimed at guiding urban development activities. EA frameworks such as TOGAF or the Zachman framework are currently deployed in enterprises to provide guide towards IT development [3].

Currently, EA adoption is significantly low irrespective of the benefits urban environments can derived from implementing EA. Similarly, there is fewer quantitative studies that examines the impact and benefits of EA for urban development. Along this line of thought, this research aims to address the following research questions:

- What are the benefits of adopting EA in smart city context?
- What are the issues that influences the adoption of EA in smart city context?

Given the lack of empirical grounded EA studies in smart city domain, this study provides a quantitative investigation of the issues that impacts the adoption of EA by practitioners in a smart city project. Findings from this study contributes by providing discussion for the observable issues faced by organizations when they adopt EA. The findings provide researchers and practitioners with insights into improving EA adoption. This paper is organized as follows: In the next section, the literature review is described. In section 3 the methodology employed is discussed. Section 4 is the results, and section 5 is the discussion. Finally, the conclusion is presented in section 6.

2. Literature Review

Several studies have been directed to explore EA adoption in institutions among these studies Foorthuis et al. [7] researched on EA benefits and conformance in systems development. The researchers aimed at identifying several significant benefits that have not yet been fully realized in organizations. Gong and Janssen [5] explored causal factors that impacts the failure of EA based on literature review. The authors aimed to investigate the factors influencing EA failure in practice based on deployed approaches, tools, and methods to create business value. Ajer and Olsen [8] explored the challenges of EA based on a case study. Their study aimed at providing an understanding of the main issues faced by organizational acceptance of EA in projects. Al-Kharusi et al. [9] provided a comprehensive research perspective view for EA. Findings from the study provided a foundation for new researchers in EA domain through presentation of research theories and methodologies which are required in designing future EA studies.

Sobczak [1] implemented an EA-based model for management of smart cities for defining the main components and outlining directions for future improvements. This helps in achieving transformation of cities into smart cities. Weiss et al. [10] studied the effectiveness and institutionalization of EA management grounded on institutional theory by proposing nine hypotheses which were validated grounded on quantitative empirical data. The author aimed at actualizing EA management benefits across organizations. Jahani et al. [11] assessed EA readiness within enterprises based on a developed model. The authors identified key factors which are important in evaluating organizations. Findings from their study aid organizations to evaluate their readiness before implementing EA in practice, thereby identifying any existing issues.

Findings from the literature [2]; [6] indicated that EA provides cities with the capacity to identify and make suitable changes, providing flexibility and stability in the city's operations. EA can be seen as an approach supported by a framework which is able to organize many facets that constitute the fundamental crux of city's services in a holistic way [12]; [13]. While findings from prior studies [3]; [4] suggest that EA provides several benefits to enterprises and cities the issues or determinants that negatively impacts their realization are widely unexplored. However, studies that explores and provides understanding of the issues that affects EA realization is highly worthwhile both from a theoretical and practical point of view [14]; [15]. Thus, this current study adds to the body of knowledge by providing benefits of adopting EA in smart cities and presenting the issues that influences the adoption of EA in smart city context.

3. Methods

This research employs a quantitative survey method using a questionnaire instrument. The questionnaire was developed to collect data on researchers and practitioner's perception on EA adoption

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in smart city project using purposive sampling. Each respondent is familiar with enterprise architecture adoption in smart city domain. The data was collected from respondents from 18 organizations in Norway and Ireland involved in the smart city project +CityxChange (<https://cityxchange.eu/>) where an EA framework was developed. The data collection took place between November 2020 to January 2021 by the means of the online survey questionnaire. Invitations were sent in November 2020 and in January 2021 additionally reminder was sent to participants to partake in the survey.

The first section of the questionnaire provides an introduction of the research to prospective participants and consent was obtained from the eligible respondents. The second section collect data as regards to the demographic information of the respondents (gender, age, organization type, type of services primarily provided, primary role, and years of experience with EA), based on an ordinal scale. The third section of the questionnaire collected data based on the respondent's perception towards the adoption of EA and usefulness of EA use case scenarios for smart cities to support urban development. The data helps towards the validation of the EA framework that was developed in the +CityxChange project [16], which comprises of seven layers (context, service, business, application and data processing, data space, technologies, and physical infrastructures), and perspectives (stakeholder and data). The question items were measured based on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Data collected from the survey was analyzed via descriptive statistics in Microsoft Excel.

4. Results

Findings from the data as regards to gender suggest that 92 % are male and 8 % are female as seen in Figure 1a.

Fig. 1. (a) Gender distribution of respondents; (b) Age distribution of respondents

Also, regarding the age distribution results from Figure 1b suggest that 38% of the respondents are between the age of 41-50 years, then 31% are between the age of 20-30 years. Also, 23% are between the age of 31-40 years and lastly 8% are between the age of 51-60 years.

In terms of the type of organization results from Figure 2a show that 53.8% of the respondents presently work in a private organization, whereas 23.1% are from the university, 15.4% are from research organization, and lastly 7.7% presently work at city council or municipality.

Fig. 2. (a) Type of organization distribution of respondents; (b) Type of organization distribution of respondents

As regards to the type of services results from Figure 2b reveal that 23.1% of the respondents work in enterprises that provides data related and innovation related services to citizens in smart cities. Whereas 15.4% provides ICT infrastructure related and 7.7% provides energy related services. The other 30.8% provides other types of services such as research focusing on citizen engagement, economics, planning, data analytics, and public services, housing, roads, environmental, water etc. as reported by the respondents.

Fig. 3. (a) Distribution of experience with EA adoption; (b) Distribution of experience with smart city projects

Results from Figure 3a indicate that 38.5% of the respondents have experience with EA for about 6 months to one year. Then, 30.8% have less than 6-month experience with adopting EA and 23.1% have prior experience of about 1-3 years. Lastly, 7.7% has experience of between 4-5 years.

Additionally, results from Figure 3b indicate that 76.9% have experience with smart city projects for about 1-3 years, 15.4% have experience with smart city projects for about 4-5 years, and lastly 7.7% just recently knew about smart city.

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Fig. 4 Distribution of relevance of enterprise architecture

Furthermore, results from the survey as seen in Figure 4 suggest that about 40% of the respondents believes that EA is relevant for their work as well as for the smart city project (+CityxChange). Although, 10% of the respondents feel EA is not relevant for their work.

Fig. 5. Perception of respondents in relation to the developed EA framework [16], relevance

Results from the survey as seen in Figure 5 suggest that the respondents neither agree nor disagree with the usefulness of EA framework [16], in their current work.

Also, 60% of the respondents agree that EA framework [16], is useful for the current smart city project.

Besides, the results suggest that the EA framework [16], is easy to understand and use.

Lastly, the respondents agree that they will recommend the EA framework [16], to their colleagues in their organization and 60% states that the EA framework [16], will be used for future work.

Fig. 6. Perception of respondents in relation to the developed EA framework relevance to knowledge transfer

As seen in Figure 6, 80% of the respondents stated that the EA framework could help in discussions with colleagues and/or collaboration within my organisation, the EA framework could help when sharing knowledge across cities, and the EA framework could help with reusing knowledge.

In addition, 70% of the respondents confirmed that the EA framework could help with sharing knowledge within their organisation.

Also, 60% highlighted that the EA framework could help when explaining use cases and solution architectures to colleagues. Lastly, 50% stated that the EA framework could help with capturing knowledge within their organizations.

Likewise, results from Figure 7 suggest that 60% of the respondents strongly agree that they will recommend use case models modelling in the developed EA framework to colleagues in their organisations.

Also, 50% of the respondents agree that they will employ use case models for future work and the use case models have helped them to clarify details about use cases of services developed to make cities smarter.

Additionally, 60% of the respondents indicated that they find it easy to describe a scenario using the use case models and 50% believes the use case models are easy to be understood.

Lastly, 70% indicated that use case models are useful for smart city project and 40% feel that overall use case models are useful for their work.

Fig. 7. Perception of respondents in relation to EA framework relevance

5. Discussion

The purpose of this study is to investigate how practitioners can motivate a greater adoption of EA to support cities into smart cities. By means of the survey this research provide evidence on the issues and benefits of EA adoption in urban environment. Therefore, this study explores the impact of EA adoption in smart city context. Data was collected from survey questionnaire and the results suggest that EA can support cities to develop strategies and integrate them with existing urban processes as mentioned in the literature [13]. Findings from Anthony Jnr [4] posited that EA is holistic as it encompasses a wide range of spectrum from business, information, and technology to management. The scope of EA comprises of the people, processes, IT, and their inter-relationship.

EA aids synergy of IT and business elements that constitute the city`s operation. But the adoption of EA is still faced with challenges which negatively impacts the successful implementation of EA. Besides, findings from the prior studies [10]; [11] suggest that EA is becoming increasingly employed

in many large organisations, but these enterprises still struggle with truly effective adopting EA. Irrespective of the growing need for EA, there are issues that ranges from people to technology that impacts against EA adoption [13].

Findings from the survey suggest that enterprise architecture is useful to be adopted in smart city project. Additionally, the results suggest that the developed EA framework [16] is applicable to be employed in smart city towards urban development as it provides knowledge transfer, aids in modelling use case scenarios for different smart city services.

6. Conclusion

This study aims to enhance understanding of the determinants that affect EA adoption in urban context. Additionally, this study offered insight into the benefits of adopting EA in urban context and the issues that influences the adoption of EA in smart city project. Quantitative research method was employed in this study and data collected from respondents in 18 enterprises based in Norway and Ireland was used to provide evidence on the issues that influence EA adoption for smart city development. Findings from this study can contribute to both business industries, municipalities, and the academic field. Also, every study has limitations and this study is not an exception. First, cross-sectional data was collected from only two countries to provide empirical evidence on the adoption of EA in smart city project. Secondly, only fewer samples were employed in this study. Hence, there is need to collect longitudinal data from more countries and practitioners in several organizations to examine benefits of adopting EA in smart city context and the issues that influences the adoption of EA in urban context. Such data could provide insight to examine or develop a theory for EA adoption.

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